

PyHC's Story: a grassroots- fueled software community in Heliophysics

Julie Barnum

LASP | University of Colorado Boulder

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PyHC Mission Statement

Promote sustainable open-source Python software;

Improve communication and collaboration between disciplines, developers, and users;

Establish/maintain development standards;

Foster interoperability and reproducibility

Key Decision: organizational structure

- Leadership team ✓
- Steering committee ⊘ (ish)
- Regular communications ✓
- One package to rule them all ⊘
- Effort consolidation where possible ✓

Leadership

Principal Investigator
[@jibarnum](#)
Julie Barnum

Technical Lead
[@sapols](#)
Shawn Polson

Members

[@AndrewAnnex](#)
Andrew Annex

[@BaptisteCecconi](#)
Baptiste Cecconi

[@DanRyanIrish](#)
Dan Ryan

[@Dolgalad](#)
Alexandre Schulz

[@abbyazari](#)
Abby Azari

[@aburrell](#)
Angeline G. Burrell

[@aharonroberts](#)
D. Aaron Roberts

[@alex-aquila](#)
Alexandria Ware

[@ayshih](#)
Albert Shih

[@balapoduval](#)
Bala Poduval

[@blalterman](#)
B. L. Alterman

[@bryan-harter](#)
Bryan Harter

[@cadair](#)
Stuart Mumford

[@cdkharris](#)
Camilla D.K. Harris

[@darrendezeeuw](#)
Darren De Zeeuw

[@dpq](#)
David Parunakian

[@drsteve](#)
Steve Morley

[@dstansby](#)
David Stansby

[@ehsteve](#)
Steven D. Christe

[@hayesia](#)
Laura Hayes

[@jklenzing](#)
Jeffrey Klenzing

[@jmason86](#)
James Mason

[@jswoboda](#)
John Swoboda

[@jtniehof](#)
Jon Niehof

* not all-inclusive

PyHC Projects

- 83 packages
- Core Packages
 - PlasmaPy, SunPy, SpacePy, pysat, HAPI, Kamodo, pySPEDAS
- Other & Un-Evaluated Packages
- Domains
 - Solar, Heliospheric, and Geospace Sciences (Magnetosphere) and ITM
 - Model output analysis, ML, plotting, wrappers for other libraries, CDF writers, etc.

<https://pyhc.org>

Key Decision: standards

- Community
- Documentation
- Testing
- Software Maturity
- Python 3
- License

Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) Standards

Purpose: In the interest of fostering an open, welcoming, collaborative, and interoperable environment, this document lists a set of standards for the Python in Heliophysics Community. We pledge to hold ourselves to these standards to the best of our ability.

Drafted during the Heliopython Meeting of November 2018.

Agreed on 10-Dec-2018 by (in alphabetical order)

A. Annex (JHU), B. L. Alterman (Univ. of Michigan), A. Azari (Univ. of Michigan), W. Barnes (Rice Univ.), M. Bobra (Stanford), B. Cecconi (Observatoire de Paris), S. Christe (NASA GSFC), J. Coxon (Univ. of Southampton), A. DeWolfe (LASP), A. Halford (Aerospace Corporation), B. Harter (LASP), J. Ireland (NASA GSFC), J. Jahn (SwRI), J. Klenzing (NASA GSFC), M. Liu (SunPy), J. Mason (NASA GSFC), R. McGranaghan (NASA JPL), S. Mumford (Aperio Software), N. Murphy (CfA), S. Murray (Trinity College Dublin), J. Niehof (Univ. of New Hampshire), M.D. Nguyen (Lomonosov Moscow State Univ.), R. Panneton (CU/LASP), A. Pembroke (NASA GSFC), D. Pérez-Suárez (University College London), C. Piker (Univ. of Iowa), A. Roberts (NASA GSFC), D. Ryan (NASA GSFC), S. Savage (NASA GSFC), J. Smith (NASA GSFC, Catholic Univ.), D. Stansby (Imperial College London), J. Vandegriff (JHU/APL), R. S. Weigel (George Mason University), S. Yu (NJIT)

Key Decision: standards

Name	Description	Code	Docs	Site	Contact	Community	Documentation	Testing	Software Maturity	Python 3	License
HAPI Client	Access time series data access from many sources				Bob Weigel	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
Kamodo	Kamodo is an official NASA open-source python package built upon the functionalization of datasets.				Darren De Zeeuw	Partially met	Good	Partially met	Good	Good	Good
PlasmaPy	A Python package for plasma physics				Nick Murphy	Good	Good	Good	Partially met	Good	Good
pysat	Management and analysis tool for satellite and radar data.				Russell Stoneback	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
pySPEDAS	Tools for				Nick	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good

Current PyHC Challenge: structure

- PyHC structure
 - Not small
 - Not one package
- Two viewpoints
 - Basic interpretation
 - Standards-based interpretation
- Path forward?
 - Tiering
 - PHEPs

Key Decision: tiering

- Levels depending on status
- Benefits per level
- Compromise between
 - Basic interpretation
 - Standards-based interpretation
- No one left behind

Key Decision: PHEPs

- PyHC Enhancement Proposal (PHEP)
 - Standards PHEP: new or modified standard for PyHC packages
 - Informational PHEP: design issue, or provides general guidelines or information to the community, but does not propose a standard
 - **Process PHEP: process surrounding PyHC, or proposes a change to a process**
- Create two PHEPs:
 - Package tiering
 - PyHC package affiliation
- Voted on by community

Lessons Learned

- Define your goals
- Consensus can be tough
- Be malleable
- Reuse/adapt past efforts
- Communicate and collaborate
- Funding advocacy
- Community sustainability

planetarypy

Overview

NASA NSPIRES

Research Opportunities in Space and Earth Sciences 2024 (ROSES-2024)

Number:	Directorate:	Type:	Status:
NNH24ZDA001N	Science Mission Directorate	NASA Research Announcement	Open

Dates

Option

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us Area

Scientific Innovation (CSSI)

A community platform for Big Data geoscience

Suggested Discussion Topics

- Community software support
 - Funding (creation, sustainment, standards compliance)
 - Software review - incentives & funding?
 - Cross-divisional support?
- Connecting existing efforts
 - Software communities (U.S. and international; not just Python)
 - Software categories
 - Heliophysics/space physics spectrum
 - Combination of various workshop outcome reports
- Standards
 - What requires conformity? Level of implementation?
 - How to handle non-conventional software? Retired software?

Connect with PyHC

- PyHC website
 - <https://pyhc.org>
- PyHC YouTube
 - <https://www.youtube.com/@pythoninheliophysicscommun3732>
- Chat rooms
 - Element Chat:
<https://app.element.io/#/room/#heliopython:openastronomy.org>
 - Slack (bridged to Element)
- PyHC mailing list
 - <https://heliopython.org/contact/>
 - Info on upcoming PyHC telecons and meetings
- Further questions? Want to get your project added to the ecosystem? Drop me a line.
 - Julie.Barnum@lasp.colorado.edu

Website

YouTube

Slack Invite